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European Polar Research Area**

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**Update of the stakeholder map developed in EU-
PolarNet 1 in cooperation with the EU Polar
Cluster projects**

Submission of Deliverable

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This up-dated stakeholder map has been compiled in cooperation with EU-PolarNet2 partners, and the [EU Polar Cluster](#). We describe what the stakeholder groups are, which important stakeholders are directly involved in EU-PolarNet 2, and which stakeholders can be reached through the EU Polar Cluster and other relevant projects. Special attention is given to the role of researchers and research institutes as stakeholders and to the Indigenous rightsholders in the research prioritisation process.

1 Introduction

In the first EU-PolarNet project we developed a stakeholder map¹ that is updated in this document. With this updated map we will ensure that the most relevant stake- and rightholders will be involved in the prioritisation of Polar research needs and the co-design of Polar research actions.

The stakeholder engagement process in EU-PolarNet 2 will act upon the recommendations as described in the [White Paper on status of stakeholder engagement in the Polar Regions](#)² developed in EU-PolarNet 1. Two of these recommendations are most relevant for this mapping exercise.

1) Engagement through intermediaries

When engaging with a stakeholder for the first time, it is advisable to work via an intermediary, an organization representing them or a person who can act as a liaison to the project. A liaison person is someone who knows personally the stakeholders that the project would like to engage with.

2) Trust building

In this stakeholder map we carefully map not only the stakeholder intermediaries, but also how we will communicate with these intermediaries. We aim to avoid stakeholder fatigue, build on existing (often long-lasting) relations between researchers or projects and their stakeholders and avoid too many researchers reaching out to the same stakeholders. We therefore also map the way we will communicate with the most important identified intermediaries.

Relevant definitions as described in the research proposal

Stakeholders are those who are potentially affected by or concerned about, interested in, important to, or having any influence on the Polar research agenda or will be end-users of Polar research outcomes. Stakeholders include a wide variety of public and private sectors including policy, business, governmental and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and the wider society, including local and Indigenous peoples (rightholders).

Indigenous Peoples are hereafter referred to as rightholders. United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 13 September 2007, 61/295.

2 Outline of this stakeholder map

In the stakeholder map from EU-PolarNet 1 (2016) nine key stakeholder groups were identified (see chapter 3 of this Deliverable), the first being the research community itself. The research community will be further addressed in chapter 6. For the other eight groups we refer to chapter 3.2.

In the first EU-PolarNet project, we have included a broad range of stakeholders in the process towards, and in the writing of, the Integrated European Polar Research Programme³. The relationship that we built with them is reflected in their roles in EU-PolarNet 2. Several stakeholders are included as full beneficiaries (WOC, EPB, ICR and AMAP), or in the [Advisory Board](#), the Policy Advisory Board, and the Polar Expert Group, see chapter 4.

¹ https://eu-polarnet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/D4-5_A-stakeholder-map_new.pdf

² <https://eu-polarnet.eu/stakeholder-engagement-in-the-polar-research/>

³ <https://eu-polarnet.eu/the-integrated-european-polar-research-programme/>

For this updated stakeholder map, we will also use contacts that are built with stakeholders and end-users by the EU Polar Cluster. These projects are engaged with relevant stakeholders and have built a relationship with them. Together, the EU Polar Cluster has a large network of stakeholders and end-users as described in chapter 5. For this map, we have reached out to all individual cluster projects to map their stakeholders and end-users, and made a first draft of a living stakeholder document. This Google document is shared amongst all EU Polar Cluster partners and forms not only an important overview of their own stakeholders, but also an important document for stakeholder cooperation. Special attention is given to the Indigenous rightsholders, who are addressed in chapter 7. In the last chapter of this updated stakeholder map, we have given an overview of other projects and organisations that we consider as relevant intermediaries and stakeholders.

3 The different stakeholder groups

3.1 Arctic, Antarctic and non-polar stakeholders

In EU-PolarNet 2 we will reach out to both Arctic and Antarctic institutional stakeholders. In general, Antarctic stakeholders seem better coordinated, as there are fewer organisations that play a more central role in the Antarctic. Any activities in Antarctica are governed through the Antarctic Treaty System (ATS) regulations provided by the Antarctic Treaty itself, along with three international agreements that together make the Antarctic Treaty System (ATS): (1) Convention for conservation of Antarctic Seals - CCAS (1972) (2) Convention on the conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources - [CCAMLR](#) (1980), (3) Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty, also known as the Madrid Protocol (1991). The Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research ([SCAR](#)) is charged with initiating, developing and coordinating high quality international scientific research in the Antarctic region (including the Southern Ocean), and provides objective and independent scientific advice to the ATS and other organizations such as the [UNFCCC](#) and [IPCC](#) on issues of science and conservation affecting the management of Antarctica and the Southern Ocean. The Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programs ([COMNAP](#)) brings together all the National Antarctic Programs, the organizations that have responsibility for delivering and supporting scientific research in the Antarctic Treaty Area.

The ATS (including [CCAMLR](#)), [SCAR](#), and [COMNAP](#) work with national contact persons/points. There is an overarching NGO organisation (Antarctic and Southern Ocean Coalition - [ASOC](#)) and tourism is regulated via the International Association for Antarctic Tourist Organisations ([IAATO](#)). Besides tourism, the only other industry allowed in the Southern Ocean is fisheries (regulated by CCAMLR). There are also Polar Technology Hubs (eg the Tasmanian Polar Network), and an informal network of the Antarctic Gateway Cities (Christchurch, Hobart, Cape Town, Ushuaia, Punta Arenas). The International Antarctic Institute (IAI) is a global consortium of universities and agencies that provide university-level education and conduct research in Antarctica. In general, even though there are seemingly fewer stakeholder organisations in Antarctica but individually, each of these organisations have a very large global reach and membership.

In the Arctic a large number and range of stakeholders including the Indigenous rightsholders exists. There is a growing focus on the sustainable economic development of the Arctic, with a broad variety of industries and businesses. Many different communities, governments and other organisations with different societal needs and research interests have to be involved. There are several bodies that play an important role, like the [Arctic Council](#), [IASC](#), [IASSA](#), [FARO](#) and for the industry the Arctic Economic Council and for instance the Arctic Expedition Cruise Operator – [AECO](#). But still many

stake- and rightsholders are not represented by these organisations and no overall global coordination of stakeholder engagement exists.

Some important stakeholder organisations work in both polar regions. The European Polar Board (EPB) is an independent organisation focused on major strategic priorities in the Arctic and Antarctic, and members include research institutes, logistics operators, funding agencies, scientific academies and government ministries from across Europe. Similarly, the Asian Forum for Polar Science ([AFoPS](#)) and the Reunión de Administradores de Programas Antárticos Latinoamericanos ([RAPAL](#)) are parallel organisations in Asia and South America respectively. The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists ([APECS](#)) is an international and interdisciplinary organization for early career researchers, professionals, educators and others with interests in Polar and Alpine regions and the wider cryosphere. The International Polar Heritage Committee ([IPHC](#)) is an NGO focusing on the preservation and protection of polar (Arctic and Antarctic) heritage.

When it comes to the non-polar stakeholders you can even state that this group consists basically of every country in the globe which will be affected by climate change effects in the polar regions. The non-polar stakeholders include also companies and business that are based outside the polar regions but do operate also in the polar regions.

3.2 Update on stakeholder groups as defined in EU-PolarNet 1

In this chapter we give an updated description of stakeholder groups as described in the stakeholder map¹ developed in the first EU-PolarNet project.

Parliament and policy

For the EU-PolarNet 2 project, the European Commission and the European Parliament are still key stakeholders. EU-PolarNet 2 can build on the relationship that has been established within the first EU-PolarNet project.

Other important parliaments and policy bodies are the national governments of the EU and Arctic countries, the [Arctic Council](#), the [Arctic Economic Council](#), the [Barents Regional Council](#) and the Antarctic Treaty system (including [CCAMLR](#)), the countries that signed the Antarctic Treaty as well as the governance organisations of regional and local communities in the Arctic.

European public and organisations

In EU-PolarNet 1 we named here only the European public. We have added here other European organisations as stakeholders that deal with the consequences of changing polar ice and weather patterns. Since all European countries that conduct polar research are represented in the EU-PolarNet 2 project, all partners play an important role in reaching out to their own populations.

Local Arctic communities and Indigenous communities

There is increasing understanding for the importance and necessity of incorporating local and Indigenous Knowledge in scientific observation and research. For the inclusion of Indigenous rightsholders we refer to chapter 4.

In the first stakeholder map we concluded that the non-Indigenous communities are not as well organised as the Indigenous communities. They can be reached through the local, regional and national governments.

Polar Organisations

In both the Arctic and Antarctic there is a group of very well-functioning organisations that either are part of the project, or are key stakeholder partners for the EU-PolarNet, for example, organisations like the EPB, the [Arctic Council](#) and its working groups. EU-PolarNet 2 has established good contacts with these organisations that we can build further upon.

NGOs

The NGOs can be divided into those engaged in environmental issues such as [Greenpeace](#) and [WWF](#) and those that have a focus on the indigenous rights, for instance the [Permanent Participants](#) of the Arctic Council. There are also overarching NGO organisations like [ASOC](#), and EU-PolarNet has developed a good working relationship with these organisations.

International networks and agencies

These include amongst others the Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes ([COMNAP](#)), the Forum of Arctic Research Operators ([FARO](#)), networks, like [UARctic](#), [SEARCH](#), [APECS](#), Arctic Science Partnership ([ASP](#)) and [ArcticNet](#). EU-PolarNet has developed good relations with all these networks and agencies.

The media

The media can be used as a way to reach stakeholders, but is also a stakeholder in its own right; however, we do not consider them as a key stakeholder in EU-PolarNet 2.

Business and Industry

This is a large and important stakeholder group for EU-PolarNet 2. In table 2 we included the overview of relevant business and industry sectors as mapped in the EU-PolarNet 1 stakeholder map⁴. For the EU, we can add that industries that support the Green Deal have become more important. The World Ocean Council ([WOC](#)) is a global, cross-sectoral ocean industry leadership alliance committed to “Corporate Ocean Responsibility”, developed by and for the private sector. WOC is and has been a full partner in both EU-PolarNet projects.

4 Stakeholders directly involved in EU-PolarNet 2

Different stakeholder representatives are directly involved in EU-PolarNet 2. This involvement is for a large part based on the relations that EU-PolarNet 1 developed with its stakeholders. In this chapter we describe which stakeholders and rightsholders are involved in EU-PolarNet 2 and which groups they represent.

4.1 Consortium partners

The European Polar Board

The European Polar Board ([EPB](#)) is an independent organisation focused on major strategic priorities in the Arctic and Antarctic. EPB Members include research institutes, logistics operators, funding agencies, scientific academies and government ministries from across Europe.

The World Ocean Council

The World Ocean Council ([WOC](#)) is a full partner of EU-PolarNet 2. The World Ocean Council is a global, cross-sectoral ocean industry leadership alliance committed to “Corporate Ocean

⁴ https://eu-polarnet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/D4-5_A-stakeholder-map_new.pdf

Responsibility”, developed by and for the private sector, with a unique and multi-sectoral approach to address cross-cutting issues affecting ocean sustainable development, science and stewardship of the seas. Via the WOC network we can reach their network of 35.000+ ocean industry stakeholders. This includes intergovernmental bodies, governments, business associations and foundations, NGOs and others. See for more information see their website: <https://www.oceancouncil.org/about-us/accreditations/>.

The Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme

As one of the working groups of the Arctic Council, [AMAP](#) will play an important role in acting as an intermediary for this intergovernmental forum. Via AMAP, EU-PolarNet 2 has also a direct link with [SAON](#), the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks.

International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry

Another important consortium partner is the International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry ([ICR](#)). For their role in engaging with the Indigenous communities we refer further to chapter 4.

Other partners

All other partners are research institutes, universities or research councils. They represent the research community of the country they are located in. Many of the consortium members are also active in other polar organisations, like [UARctic](#), [IASC](#), [IASSA](#), [APECS](#), the [working groups](#) of the Arctic Council, [FARO](#), [SCAR](#), [COMNAP](#) and [CCAMLR](#).

4.2 The EU-PolarNet Advisory Board

One of the objectives of the EU-PolarNet 2 Advisory Board is to provide strategies for capacity building related to meaningful stakeholder involvement. The board will also give advice on the involvement of different stakeholder groups throughout the project. The members of the Advisory Board have been carefully chosen to represent different important stakeholders. An overview of the board members can be found in table 1.

Table 1: Members of the EU-PolarNet Advisory Board

Name	Representation
Nicolas Dubreuil (chair)	He works for a consulting company that aims to promote and help scientists in the polar environment by providing privately funded vessels. He is also involved in developing science projects for Ponant , a polar cruise operator. Ponant is a member of AECO (the Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators) and IAATO (International Association for Antarctic Tour Operators)
Anne Rännäli-Kontturi	International Affairs Manager at the city of Oulu, Finland and member of the Arctic Mayors Forum . The Arctic Mayors’ Forum is an organization that aims to give local governments a voice in the development of the Arctic. Members represent represents local governments in the Arctic states of USA, Russia, Canada, Iceland, Greenland, Faroe Islands, Finland and Norway
Antonio Meloni	Former President of the Italian National Scientific Commission for Antarctica (CSNA)
Claire Christian	Executive director of the Antarctic and Southern Ocean Coalition (ASOC). ASOC is the only NGO working full time to preserve Antarctica and the surrounding Southern Ocean

Elle Merete Omma	Head of EU Unit of the Saami Council . The Saami Council is an NGO with Saami member organizations in Finland, Russia, Norway and Sweden.
Gerlis Fugmann	Executive Secretary of the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)
Hannah Grist	Work Package Leader in Blue Action (EU Polar Cluster) and communication specialist
Marina Villegas	Spanish Research Council (CSIC) delegate for Madrid regional affairs, former director of the Spanish Polar Committee

4.3. The EU-PolarNet Policy Advisory Board

The role of the Policy Advisory Board (PAB) is to provide up-to-date, evidenced-based, explicit and implementable recommendations, advice or briefings on Polar-related questions on behalf of the whole European Polar community. The PAB has the following roles:

- to provide policy advice on issues related to the Polar Regions on an ad-hoc basis,
- to respond to requests from EU-PolarNet 2, and through EU-PolarNet 2 from the EC and other national policy makers, to issues related to the Polar Regions,
- to consult with national Polar experts, for the benefit of EU and national policy makers,
- to support EU-PolarNet 2 in identifying important topics and speakers for the planned policy briefings.

The following stakeholder representatives (from non-beneficiary organisations) are PAB members:

- Mark van der Hulst, CEO of [Oceanwide Expeditions](#), expedition style cruises to the Arctic, North Atlantic, Antarctic and Sub-Atlantic Islands.
- Susan Barr representing the International Polar Heritage Committee ([IPHC](#)). The IPHC is an NGO focusing on the preservation and protection of polar (Arctic and Antarctic) heritage.
- Mikael Thinghuus CEO of [Royal Greenland](#) a fishing company.
- Volker Rachold, Head of the [German Arctic Office](#).

5 The EU Polar Cluster

The EU Polar Cluster representatives will act as important intermediaries in the stakeholder engagement process. The stakeholder task group of the EU Polar Cluster aims to better coordinate and collaborate on stakeholder activities in order to reduce stakeholder fatigue, respect relations that have already been built by projects with stakeholders and rightsholders and try to be more efficient.

A short overview of the [EU Polar Cluster members](#) (in alphabetical order) with a short description of the project and their most important stakeholders is given below. Some projects have mainly the science community as a stakeholder, others work with a very broad mix of stakeholders and rightsholders. Also, the way each EU Polar Cluster project interact with its stakeholders differs.

Due to the pandemic the first EU Polar Cluster [stakeholder task group](#) meetings took place online. This made it more difficult for the different project representatives to get to know each other. We therefore decided to have on-line meetings with all individual EU Polar Cluster project representatives in order to get to know each other better (trust building), to get to know who are each projects' stakeholders, the way they are engaging with stakeholders in the project and to discuss strategies how we can best cooperate together. The results of these meetings are reflected in a Google sheets document that can be accessed by all cluster projects. This is a living document aiming to inform all cluster projects about which stakeholders each project is interacting with. If

projects know from each other who their respective stakeholders are, they can better work together and streamline the communications and interaction with overlapping stakeholders.

Several stakeholder contact persons from projects that are near finishing indicated that they will remain a contact person for the project's stakeholders after the project has finished.

The EU Polar Cluster projects that started most recently (CHARTER, JustNorth, ArcticHubs, Arctic PASSION) are currently compiling their own stakeholder maps. A more integrated approach in these mapping exercises and the best way to work with the Google sheet document will be discussed in the next stakeholder task-group meeting in October 2021.

In this overview you will find in between brackets whether the project is focused on the Arctic, Antarctic or Polar.

APPLICATE (Arctic): Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: modelling, observing system design and linkages associated with a changing Arctic climate. APPLICATE aims to establish an effective dialogue with key stakeholders. Stakeholder engagement aims to disseminate the project results widely, but also to exploit means such as project and data portals through international frameworks ([WMO](#), [ICSU](#), [SAON](#) etc.), to implement enhancements in operational prediction systems and transition into Copernicus services ([C3S](#)), to involve partners from both weather and climate communities, and to develop a training programme in collaboration with the Association of Early Polar Career Scientists ([APECS](#)).

ARCSCAR (Arctic): The overall aim of ARCSAR is to fast-track uptake of existing innovations and knowledge by practitioners, predict future needs for innovation and knowledge, and identify priorities for security and standardisation across the Arctic and North Atlantic (ANA) region. Stakeholders include institutions in security and emergency responses, cruise operators, meteorological institutes and coastal administrations.

Arctic PASSION (Arctic) will address the urgent need for coordinated and accessible Earth observations and information services for the Arctic Regions. The project aims to include a very broad variety of stakeholders, including a broad range of communities, industries, NGOs and businesses.

ArcticHubs (Arctic) is a multi-disciplinary international collaboration that aims to develop research-led practice-based solutions to the urgent challenges faced in the Arctic. Their key stakeholders include forestry, fish farming, mining, tourism and Indigenous communities.

ARICE (Arctic)- Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium: A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research in the Arctic. Main stakeholders are the maritime industry, polar cruise operators and operators of research vessels.

Beyond EPICA (Antarctic) aims to retrieve a continuous ice core to bedrock in Antarctica, covering the climate history of the Mid-Pleistocene Transition and beyond in order to improve climate prediction. Their main stakeholders are researchers and especially climate modellers.

Blue-Action (Arctic) Blue-Action evaluates the impact of Arctic warming on the Northern Hemisphere and develops new techniques to improve forecast accuracy at sub-seasonal to decadal scales. Blue-Action works to understand and simulate the linkages between the Arctic and the global climate system, and the Arctic's role in generating weather patterns associated with hazardous conditions and climatic extremes. Stakeholders include local and national decision makers, developers of climate services, local Arctic communities in Russia and Greenland, national weather services, winter tourism and fishing industry and NGOs operating at local level and international level (Greenpeace).

CAPARDUS (Arctic) is a coordination and support action project aimed at capacity building to support sustainable development in the Arctic. Subcontractors of the project are Exchange of Local Observations and Knowledge of the Arctic ([ELOKA](#)), USA, University of Alaska Fairbanks - International Arctic Research Center ([UAF/IARC](#)), USA, Center for Support of Indigenous Peoples of the North ([CSIPN](#)), Russia and Element84 ([E84](#)), USA. Stakeholders include service providers, indigenous and local communities, commercial operators and governance bodies.

CHARTER (Arctic): Drivers and Feedbacks of Changes in Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity. Stakeholders include the extractive industry, local and regional administrations, NGOs (public welfare and environmental protection), Indigenous communities and reindeer tourism.

ECOTIP (Arctic): Ecological tipping cascades in the Arctic Seas focusses on understanding and predicting changes in Arctic marine biodiversity and implications for two vitally important marine ecosystem services: fisheries production, which is the economic lifeblood of many Arctic communities, and carbon sequestration, which has important feedbacks to the global climate. Stakeholders include the fishing industry, fishing communities and other fishing organisations in Greenland.

European Polar Board (Polar): Although not an EU project, the European Polar Board (EPB) is also included in the EU Polar Cluster. The EPB is an independent organisation focused on major strategic priorities in the Arctic and Antarctic. EPB Members include research institutes, logistics operators, funding agencies, scientific academies and government ministries from across Europe.

FACE-IT (Arctic): To enable adaptive co-management of social-ecological fjord systems in the Arctic in the face of rapid cryosphere and biodiversity changes. Stakeholders include local and national decision makers, fisheries and tourism.

FORCeS (Polar) aims to understand and reduce the long-standing uncertainty in anthropogenic aerosol radiative forcing, which is crucial in order to increase confidence in climate projections. Stakeholders include Dept. Environment Finland and Sweden, Swedish climate policy council, IIASA - International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme and Finnish Climate Panel.

iCUPE (Arctic): Integrative and Comprehensive Understanding on Polar Environments. Stakeholders include national and European weather services and environmental agencies and observing networks. Their stakeholders include European Environment Agencies, intergovernmental, organisations, local government and environmental administration and national and European weather services

INTAROS (Arctic): to develop an integrated Arctic Observation System (iAOS) by extending, improving and unifying existing systems in the different regions of the Arctic. The INTAROS project and its partners has during the recent two years had several contacts with stakeholders to collect as detailed as possible information on their requirements for products and services to optimise their operations in the Arctic including increased safety. These stakeholders include shipping communities, shipping industry, oil/gas, fishing industry, aquaculture and environmental agencies.

INTERACT (Arctic): to build capacity for identifying, understanding, predicting and responding to diverse environmental changes throughout the wide environmental and land-use envelopes of the Arctic. A network of 89 terrestrial research stations. Stakeholders include local and Indigenous communities and tourism.

JUSTNORTH (Arctic) aims to assess the viability of economic development of the Arctic through sustainability and justice perspectives, while gaining insights on the positive and negative impacts, risks and benefits of key economic activities. Stakeholders include energy, mining and tourism industry and cities and municipalities in Northern Sweden, Finland and Russia.

KEPLER (Polar) is a multi-partner initiative, built around the operational European Ice Services and Copernicus information providers, to prepare a roadmap for Copernicus to deliver an improved European capacity for monitoring and forecasting the Polar Regions.

NUNATARYUK (Arctic) determines the impacts of thawing coastal and subsea permafrost on the global climate, and will develop targeted and co-designed adaptation and mitigation strategies for the Arctic coastal population. Stakeholders include hunter and trapper communities and several other local communities.

PROTECT (Polar) assesses and project changes in the land-based cryosphere with quantified uncertainties, to produce robust global, regional and local projections of SLR on a wide range of timescales. Stakeholders include Greenland Survey. timescales. PROTECT distinguishes two groups of stakeholders, global and regional stakeholders. The global stakeholders are needed assess decisions relevant to sea-level rise that these stakeholders are facing within their institutional context, in order to identify what kind of information and coastal climate services are required for 2050, 2100 and longer timescales. The regional stakeholders – directly involved in the project through four case studies, are aimed at co-developing and co-producing sea-level projections and coastal climate services, illustrating the added value of the sea-level projections produced within PROTECT at local scales.

SIOS (Arctic), the Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth System aims for better coordination and harmonisation of research activities, research infrastructure and data of international partners in Svalbard, reduced footprint of science in the Arctic, technological spin-offs from innovative technology used in science in harsh conditions. Stakeholders include researchers and academia, policy experts, policy makers, funding agencies including EU and national digital agencies and civil society, NGOs, citizens.

SO-CHIC (Antarctic) - Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate: To understand and quantify variability of heat and carbon budgets in the Southern Ocean through an investigation of the key processes controlling exchanges between the atmosphere, ocean and sea ice using a

combination of observational and modelling approaches. Stakeholders include NGOs, European Commission services and policy makers, European and international initiatives and related relevant projects.

TiPACCs (Antarctic) is investigating the possibility of sudden and large changes in Antarctic Climate Components.

6 The polar research community as a stakeholder group

The polar research community will play an important role in the research prioritisation process of EU-PolarNet 2. They will be reached in different ways:

- Via the consortium partners: the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium includes research institutes from all European countries that have been tasked to represent their national polar research community. In that way EU-PolarNet 2 can reach out to all European polar researchers.
- Via the EU Polar Cluster
- Via the large research cooperation organisations [SCAR](#), [IASC](#), [APECS](#), [UArctic](#) and [IASSA](#)
- Via the Polar Expert Group (PEG)

Consortium partners have nominated experts for the Polar Expert Group (PEG). The main aim of the PEG is to prioritise and specify the key societally relevant Polar Research themes on the basis of the European Polar Research Programme (EPRP), the White Papers and the European Polar strategies, also integrating stake and rightsholders' interests, both at Arctic and Antarctic level.

7 The role of Indigenous rightsholders

There is increasing understanding of the importance and necessity of incorporating local and Indigenous Knowledge in scientific observations and research. Arctic Indigenous Peoples know their lands and communities better than anyone else and must be included in the Polar research prioritisation process. The special position of the Indigenous Peoples requires a different approach to their inclusion in the research prioritisation process and other aspects of the project. Appropriate input to the project will be ensured via the International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry (ICR) as a full partner in the project, a representative from Saami Council in the Advisory Board and DAFSHE who is representing Greenland and its Indigenous communities.

Since EU-PolarNet 1 did not organise any events targeted specifically to Indigenous Communities and/or in their lands, at least one workshop will be held in the Sámi homeland (Sápmi) jointly organised by ICR and the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (via DAFSHE). EU-PolarNet 2 considers it crucial to build a trusting-relationship with the Indigenous organisations and communities and to support capacity building.

8 Other key organisations and projects

Below is an overview of other key organisations and projects that EU-PolarNet 2 is engaging with or will reach out to since they can act as good intermediaries.

Arctic Economic Council

The Arctic Economic Council ([AEC](#)) works to facilitate responsible business and economic development of the Arctic and its communities. Their goal is to share and advocate for best practices, technological solutions, and standards. They support market accessibility and provide advice and a business perspective to the work of the Arctic Council. Their members represent a wide range of businesses operating in the Arctic—from mining and shipping companies to reindeer herding and Indigenous economic development corporations. This mix of interests across business sectors ensures that their work is carried out in an inclusive and sustainable manner. Representing the wide variety of Arctic businesses, it is important for the AEC to also be the voice of small and medium-sized enterprises. Their selected business areas are Maritime transportation / Communications and IT / Aviation / Energy, including oil, gas and renewable sources / Mining / Tourism / Blue economy / Human Resources Investments and capacity building.

ESA Polar Science Cluster

EU-PolarNet 2 has discussed cooperation with the [ESA Polar Science Cluster](#). Through these projects another group of polar researchers can be reached.

IMO

The International Maritime Organization ([IMO](#)) is the United Nations specialized agency with responsibility for the safety and security of shipping and the prevention of marine and atmospheric pollution by ships. IMO's work supports the UN SDGs.

International Union for the Conservation of Nature

[IUCN](#) is a membership Union composed of both government and civil society organisations. It harnesses the experience, resources and reach of its more than 1,400 member organisations and the input of more than 18,000 experts. This diversity and vast expertise make IUCN the global authority on the status of the natural world and the measures needed to safeguard it.

Humanities and Social Science Group of SCAR

The SCAR Standing Committee on the Humanities and Social Sciences ([SC-HASS](#)) aims to initiate, develop and coordinate rigorous and high-quality international research on the Antarctic region within the Humanities and Social Sciences (HASS); to provide independent advice to the Antarctic Treaty Consultative Meetings (ATCMs) on issues requiring disciplinary expertise outside the natural sciences; and to coordinate with existing science groups on issues that call for a multidisciplinary approach.

PPP-SERA

Since there are more Arctic than Antarctic projects it is important to look for other intermediaries that have good contacts with Antarctic stakeholders. Hence, we reached out to the Polar Prediction Project Societal and Economic Research and Applications ([PPP-SERA](#)) task team. This team contributes social sciences expertise and operational know-how to the Polar Prediction Project. The PPP-SERA task team's research focuses on the needs for, and the use of, environmental information, which includes the study of decision-making processes by a diverse range of actors in the Polar Regions. Furthermore, PPP-SERA team members and contributors intend to examine pathways, methods and challenges in relation to how polar weather, water, ice and climate (WWIC) information is communicated between providers and users.

UNEP

The United Nations Environment Programme ([UNEP](#)) is the leading global environmental authority that sets the global environmental agenda, promotes the coherent implementation of the environmental dimension of sustainable development within the United Nations system, and serves as an authoritative advocate for the global environment.

WMO

[WMO](#) is a specialized agency of the United Nations (UN) with 193 Member States and Territories. It is the UN system's authoritative voice on the state and behaviour of the Earth's atmosphere, its interaction with the land and oceans, the weather and climate it produces and the resulting distribution of water resources. WMO jointly sponsors the World Climate Research Program ([WCRP](#)) and its projects like CliC and CLIVAR, amongst others.

International Science Council

The International Science Council ([ISC](#)) is a non-governmental organization with a unique global membership that brings together 40 international scientific Unions and Associations and over 140 national and regional scientific organizations including Academies and Research Councils. Important member organisations of the ICS that work in the polar regions include [SCAR](#), [IASC](#), [IASSA](#), [UArctic](#) among others.

The table below gives an overview of the key stakeholders and the EU Polar Cluster projects and key intermediaries that relates to these stakeholders.

Table 2: stakeholder groups and their key intermediaries and EU Polar Cluster projects

Stakeholder group	Key intermediaries and EU Polar Cluster projects
Parliament and policy	
EU Commission and EU Parliament	EU-PolarNet
Arctic Council	AMAP
Arctic Economic Council	AMAP
Barents Council	EU-PolarNet
Antarctic Treaty System	EPB, EU-PolarNet
European public	
European countries	All consortium partners
European weather organisations	APPLICATE / FORCeS / PPP-SERA /iCUPE/KEPLER/PROTECT/Blue-Action
Local Arctic communities	
Arctic cities	Arctic Mayors Forum/ ArcticHubs/INTAROS
Local communities	Arctic PASSION/Blue-Action/CAPARDUS/CHARTER/INTAROS/NUNATARYUK/PROTECT
Polar Organisations	
Arctic Council	AMAP/EU-PolarNet
NGOs	
Antarctic	Antarctic and Southern Ocean Coalition (ASOC)

Stakeholder group	Key intermediaries and EU Polar Cluster projects
Arctic	Blue-Action/CHARTER /International Polar Heritage Committee (Policy Advisory Board)/ArcticPASSION/ICR and Saami Council/SIOS/ INTAROS
International networks and agencies	
UArctic	Several consortium partners are actively involved
IASSA	The stakeholder guardian is council member of IASSA
IASC	Via EU-PolarNet 2 Advisory Board
FARO	Several consortium partners are actively involved
SCAR	Several consortium partners are actively involved
COMNAP	Several consortium partners are actively involved
CCAMLR	Several consortium partners are actively involved
Environment Agencies	iCUPE/PROTECT
Business and industry sectors	
Oil and Gas	Arctic Economic Council/CHARTER/INTAROS/Blue-Action/WOC/PROTECT
Land-based mining / mineral resources	Arctic Economic Council/ArcticHubs/CHARTER
Fisheries	ECOTIP/Blue-Action/Royal Greenland (Policy Advisory Board)/INTAROS/CAPARDUS/WOC
Aquaculture	ECOTIP/ArcticHubs/INTAROS/WOC
Shipping	IMO/INTAROS/WOC/Blue-Action/CAPARDUS
Ports and infrastructure	WOC/Arctic Mayors Forum/Nunataryuk
Logistics, maritime services	ARCSAR/CAPARDUS/SIOS/Blue-Action/WOC
Tourism	EU-PolarNet/INTERACT/ARCSAR/ArcticHubs/ARICE/WOC/INTAROS/Blue-Action/CAPARDUS
Submarine cables	WOC
Wind and hydro power production	JUSTNORTH/WOC
Consulting and advisory services	ARCSAR/Arctic PASSION/INTAROS/Blue-Action/WOC
Science Technology and data	PROTECT/SIOS/ARICE
Insurances	ARCSAR/PROTECT
Marine biotechnology	WOC